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Developing MIT's LASER -- Leadership Academy for Scientists, Engineers, and Researchers -- Program

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ABSTRACT

In the midst of global shifts in how professional engineers work and learn, creative and innovative new leaders are needed to step forward in their fields to tackle the world's future challenges. Today's new leaders need to be lifelong learners, continuously reflecting on the state of their field and gaining capacity to create and lead systemic change. Towards this vision, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) is launching a new initiative, the Leadership Academy for Scientists, Engineers, and Researchers (LASER); a modular suite of online and blended educational content accompanied by on-campus opportunities, that breaks down the traditional silos between engineering and management while convening interdisciplinary approaches to leadership. LASER is by design a cross-Institute collaboration, between the Office of Open Learning, School of Engineering, Sloan School of Management, School of Architecture and Planning, Gordon Engineering Leadership Program and other programs across campus, to bring a unified MIT approach to engineering leadership.

MIT faculty from all the aforementioned schools are currently collaborating to develop and pilot 4 online courses for this new program that is expected to launch in fall 2019. This 4 course online program will lead to a professional certificate from MIT. The program is expected to provide professional engineers with the appropriate

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leadership knowledge and skills; content that is currently being underrepresented or is completely lacking from the curriculum in many traditional engineering schools.

This paper will discuss the cross disciplinary partnership between the experts from different fields as well as the implementation of the online program.

INTRODUCTION

Climate changes, water and food scarcities, a rapidly expanding population with longer life expectancies, increasing migration and displacement, looming threats of terrorism and nuclear deployment; are all posing mounting challenges for contemporary and future engineers [1-3]. Meanwhile, a Fourth Industrial Revolution is on the immediate horizon as the boundaries between the digital, physical, and biological spheres blur and intertwine. How has, and how can, engineering and science education prepare individuals with the tools and skills they need to tackle these challenges, to explore emerging frontiers, disrupt staid traditions, and develop novel, sustainable solutions for our local and global communities? What will the engineers and scientists of 2025 need to know and be able to do?

The skills for tomorrow demand both engineering expertise and leadership acumen. But, do existing engineering and science education programs prepare workers with all the skills they need? The National Academy of Engineering's 2012 forum panellists, when attempting to envision this complex education model of the future, "outlined a new vision for engineering education based on flexible, interactive, lifelong learning and the merge of activities" [4], while the World Economic Forum [5] identified ten top skills needed beyond 2020, them being: complex problem solving, critical thinking, creativity and innovation, people management, coordinating with others, emotional intelligence, judgment and decision-making, service orientation, negotiation, and cognitive flexibility. Today's engineers and scientists possess many of the skills needed for tomorrow. They are analytical, trained in systematic problem-solving with deep technical expertise, innovative, and detail-oriented. Yet, many lack the leadership, people management, knowledge transfer, and communication skills needed to be successful, as they will be progressing into higher leadership positions in their careers. To gain these capacities, MIT suggests that lifelong leadership learning and practice must not only supplement but be woven into traditional engineering and science education.

Today, many professional organizations look to programs, assessments, and recruitment techniques to better identify and nurture employees with leadership potential. Leadership conferences, retreats, and executive education programs are profitable businesses with a flurry of new offerings each year. Yet, after decades of research, organizational management expert Morgan McCall concludes that while lots of people become leaders, few become effective in part because they fail to learn "the right lessons" from their leadership learning experiences [6]. Part of the issue may be a mismatch of one-size-fits-all leadership programs that ignore disciplinary difference, failing to grow an individual's leadership capacity alongside their technical expertise.

Yet, integrating technical and field-specific expertise within leadership development and integrating the learning experience while on the job seems essential for leadership lessons to be meaningfully situated within these leaders' real world context and practice.

Dedicated leadership training for engineers, and others from fields in engineering, technology, and the sciences, is now an emerging area. However, while there is a burgeoning growth of "engineering leadership" programs, there are few scalable, cost-effective products or services in the market today that offer the convenience, flexibility, and variety of learning modalities in both leadership and technical expertise that these professionals need. Addressing this need, MIT aspires to develop an engineering leadership program through the LASER initiative.

1 THE PROGRAM

MIT's "Leadership Academy for Scientists, Engineers, and Researchers" (LASER) is a modular suite of online educational content that prepares engineers, scientists, and researchers in technical professions to become leaders.

LASER's content is focused on technical professionals, designed specifically for individual contributors, to first time managers, to project leads who are looking to take the next step in their career. For some, this means continuing to serve as an individual contributor, but with a better understanding of the underlying management environment in their organization. For others, this involves becoming a first time manager, or a mid-level manager of managers. LASER addresses all of these groups.

The LASER program draws from MIT's established institutions: the School of Engineering, Sloan Management, Gordon Engineering Leadership Program, and others across campus that are already addressing engineering leadership in their own way.

MIT faculty from the aforementioned schools are currently collaborating to develop and pilot four online courses for this new program that is expected to launch in fall 2019. This four course online program will lead to a professional certificate from MIT.

The program is expected to provide professional engineers with the appropriate leadership knowledge and skills; content that is currently being underrepresented or is completely lacking from the curriculum in many traditional engineering schools.

2 COURSES

2.1 Course One: Understanding Organizational Strategy and Capabilities

Course One follows the linkages from strategy to product definition, on to the design of work needed to build the products and the organization of that work in teams. The course builds an understanding of how these factors set the context and define the needs for leadership and demonstrate how one can lead people to work effectively in teams.

By the end of the course, students should be able to:

- Identify and evaluate your organization's strategy to align your ideas, products, and efforts with it.
- Prioritize products that create value for the end user.
- Decompose your product systems into individual tasks, relationships, and entities to organize and conceptualize your work.
- Develop new processes by utilizing the Four Principles of Dynamic Work Design.
- Identify the notion of capability and its impact with implementing change.
- Design knowledge work effectively by utilizing visual management.

2.2 Course Two: Negotiating and Applying Influence and Power

Course Two is about getting people to do what you want, when you want, the way you want.

By the end of the course, students should be able to:

- Understand key terms and strategies from negotiation and conflict resolution theory, theories of social influence (persuasion) and theories regarding the exercise of power within and between organizations.
- Build awareness of multicultural interactions in the workplace, particularly in regard to different perspectives on negotiation
- Demonstrate theory through multiple real-time role-play simulations followed by peer feedback.
- Identify tensions within co-working teams and understand how best to balance competing ideas and interests while finding common ground.
- Construct a personal theory of practice and the progress they have made in the course regarding their ideas about negotiation, social influence and the exercise of power inside organizations and multiparty situations.
- Develop the tools and the playbook needed to continue to learn from personal negotiation and organizational leadership efforts after completing the course.

2.3 Course Three: Leading Change in Organizations

Course Three explores three perspectives on organizations – strategic design, political, and cultural. All have important implications for performing effectively in the everyday operations of the firm as well as successfully undertaking change in organization.

By the end of the course, students should be able to:

- Introduce scientists, engineers, and researchers to a way to diagnose organizational problems and prescribe solutions based on three perspectives – strategic design, political and cultural.

- Introduce key terms and concepts from network, power and culture theories that are critical for accomplishing individual and collective goals.
- Provide ample opportunities to apply these perspectives and concepts through multiple video-enhanced cases and compact writing assignments.
- Provide participants with the practical tools available to them along with a sense of when to use such tools while attempting to lead or support a modest or extensive organizational change.

2.4 Course Four: Discovering and Implementing Your Leadership Strengths

Course Four combines an “inside out” with an “outside in” learning strategy where learners look “inside” to discover and develop their unique leadership strengths as well gain “outside” insights on how others view their strengths and how to develop them.

By the end of the course, students should be able to:

- Explain their distinctive leadership strengths grounded in personality, values, capabilities, and self-identity.
- Develop new leadership strengths.
- Define future leadership contributions and how to realize them.

3 LEARNING DESIGN

The design vision of the LASER curriculum, pedagogy, and learning environment is based in the latest neuroscience and cognitive behavioral science on learning, as well as best practices from years of MIT’s work in digital learning.

LASER puts evidence-based insight into action, implementing such digital learning innovations as modular content, interleaved assessments, visualizations and simulations, and adaptive hinting. By unbundling traditional semester-long content into modular, consumable units, LASER creates a learning environment that provides learners with the knowledge they need as they need it. This program design is crucial for busy professionals working to extend their education while on the job.

MIT’s founding motto *mens et manus* (meaning mind and hand) underwrites LASER’s pedagogy with course modules and resources designed for learners to apply their knowledge and skills to real-life challenges and projects. Research on expert performance suggests that it takes 10 years or 10,000 hours of dedicated practice to become an expert in a field [7]. As leadership expert D.V. Day observes [8], leaders cannot fully develop simply through passive participation in a series of workshops, seminars, and programs. Rather, leadership is developed in experiential practice. As Day underlines, “this notion of ongoing practice through day-to-day leadership activities is where the crux of development really resides” [9]. LASER is defined with

this very notion in mind – providing a platform for people to practice being leaders through modular, spaced opportunities to develop the knowledge, practice the skills and apply the learnings they need to become more effective managers and leaders in their fields.

Figure 1: LASER Learning Model

The LASER learning design offers students a repeatable learning model. As illustrated in Figure 1 above, students are asked to go through a learning cycle where they will assess, learn, practice, reflect, analyze and apply, and evaluate.

- **Assess:** For every topic, diagnostic tools help learners assess and understand their strengths and weaknesses.
- **Learn:** Students learn core concepts via engaging videos and research-based readings.
- **Practice:** Through case studies and simulation activities, LASER creates a safe place for learners to practice and build skills.
- **Reflect:** Students are asked to reflect and take stock of what they have learned.
- **Analyze and Apply:** Via real-world projects, students learn to apply, analyze, and contextualize learnings to their current jobs.
- **Evaluate:** Using post-assessment instruments, LASER measures students' outcomes and evaluates their progress.

4 CURRENT STATE AND FUTURE WORK

Before launching LASER to the market in the fall of 2019, MIT is currently running a beta program with over 300 learners drawn from the following organizations: Boeing, NASA, Fidelity, Boston Scientific, and US Air Force Institute of Technology.

As ensuring customer input and industry alignment of LASER is paramount to MIT, quantitative and qualitative data covering all aspects of the program is being collected so that MIT can improve the content, learning design, and overall user experience. MIT will continue to evaluate the program with each run of the course and use findings to improve the program in its next iteration.

While MIT will not know what enrollments are for this program until later in the summer, MIT is forecasting 3,000 learners will sign up for the inaugural run. With attendees representing a large international population with different background, LASER's aspiration is to bring together bright, curious minds from around the world and create a lasting community and knowledge base for future technical leaders as well as foster new opportunities for engagement between the MIT community and the world. Finally, LASER aspires to prepare tomorrow's technical community with the leadership skills needed to tackle the globe's grand challenges.

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